
MEASURING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES IN TOURIST FACILITIES IN THE ZLATIBOR DISTRICT USING THE SERVQUAL MODEL

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Abstract: *Satisfying the needs of users is the basic task of every organization that strives for long-term and sustainable business. Research by many authors has shown that the level of quality of delivered services is directly related to the satisfaction of the users of those services. As with all services, the quality of tourist services requires good and careful planning. Tourism, as an economic activity, is very important, which is indicated by the fact that in the most economically developed countries in the world, an average of 65% of the total number of employees is employed in the tourism sector.*

This paper gives the results of empirical research aimed at measuring the quality of services in tourist facilities of the Zlatibor district using the SERVQUAL model.

INTRODUCTION

In today's business conditions, the growth, development, stability and survival of every economy depends on the level of competitiveness, the degree of innovation, the quality of products and services, and the ability to quickly adapt to changes. Quality has an important role in setting and defining the strategy of the organization and it is the basis for achieving competitiveness and better positioning on the market¹. The market for both products and services has long become global, technologies are developing at a high speed and the flow of information is getting faster every day. Therefore, organizations must accept new business conditions and adapt to them in order to meet the needs of their users. For organizations to survive in today's business conditions and respond to the demands of their users, they must be innovative, follow the market trends, accept new and better solutions and work on the constant improvement of their products and services.

The aim of this paper is to review user satisfaction with services in tourist facilities using the SERVQUAL model.

THE IMPORTANCE OF MEASURING THE SATISFACTION TOURIST SERVICES USERS

The development of tourism became particularly intense in the middle of the 20th century. Realizing that tourism occupies a very important place in international trade exchange, most countries in the world strive to develop both domestic and foreign tourism². The satisfaction of users of tourist services is very important for the survival of the tourist business system in today's business conditions. User satisfaction tells us to what level users' requirements and expectations from the used tourist product have been met. Achieving consumer satisfaction is closely related to the achievement of management goals, the quality of the tourism business system, and especially the achievement of business excellence. Achieving business excellence requires simultaneously ensuring three aspects of quality:

¹ Milanovic M., Nikitovic Z., Vujicic S. The importance of the quality of the agricultural product for sustainable success of agricultural holding, [International Review](#), No. 3-4, pp. 105-112, Faculty of Business, Economics and Entrepreneurship, Belgrade, 2020
² Živić D., Vujčić S., Dimitrijević Lj., Održivi turizam u Republici Srbiji, Međunarodna naučna konferencija "Nove strategije i tehnologije zaštite životne sredine" Ecologica, Beograd, 2012

marketing, business and social. The marketing aspect contains a technical aspect related to product performance³:

- Product quality: durability, reliability, precision, ease of handling, maintenance, repairs, additional features and other features that maximize end user satisfaction;
- Satisfaction of customer requirements;
- Ease of use;
- Market positioning;
- Competitive advantage.

Marketing activities are all activities that make the exchange process efficient. They are aimed at identifying and satisfying the existing needs and at creating new, higher needs of existing and potential consumers, while achieving company profits. Marketing activities start from the needs and demands of consumers and include activities of research and development, engineering and production, ending with the creation of value for the consumer.⁴

If an organization wants to be successful in today's modern economy, it must radically rethink all its activities. The traditional approach to markets must be discarded in favor of simultaneous penetration of all markets at once, combined with a firm decision on insiderization (bringing producers into the enterprise through information sharing and joint participation in shaping strategies and other activities and training).⁵

Improving user satisfaction and building relationships, both with existing and potential users, should lead to achieving their loyalty and creating a loyal user. To ensure satisfaction and customer loyalty, organizations must consider the welfare of their employees and work environment, the impact of its operations and processes in the local community. The long-term effects that their products have during and after use must also be taken into account⁶. A loyal customer for an organization means the fulfillment of the main goal, which is to ensure the long-term survival of the organization in the market and achieve a competitive advantage. This means that the organization has a permanent customer who trusts it, more

³ Jelić M., FQCE model izvrsnosti u funkciji povećanja efikasnosti srpske privrede, Kvalitet, br. 19, Beograd, 2013. pp. 77

⁴ Keegan J.W. and Mc. Green, Principles of Global Marketing, Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, p. 7, 1997

⁵ Kenichy O., Nova globalna pozornica, Mate, Zagreb, 2007, pp. 244

⁶ Momcilovic O., Cvetic T., Vujcic S., Antonijevic A. The Impact of Stress and Health on Quality of Working Life of Women in SMEs in Republic of Serbia, Journal of women's entrepreneurship, Belgrade, No.1-2, 2017

repeated purchases, both of products and services, recommendation by satisfied users and an increase in the number of new users, faster return of invested funds, secure profit.

Only satisfied users whose realized service quality is higher than expected have the desire to repeat the positive experience. They expect not to have their positive experience repeated, but to have their satisfaction increased, which requires organizations to constantly improve the quality of their services. All this unequivocally says that the quality of services is ultimately evaluated through the measured satisfaction of its users.

Measuring user satisfaction is a component of measuring the performance of the quality management system of the tourism business system. The goal is to determine the extent to which the achieved quality met the requirements and needs of the users, i.e. to state whether it exceeded the expected quality.

Table 1. Overview of activities regarding the collection, processing and analysis of user data

1. Identifying the problem	2. Extraction and collection of data	3. Processing and analysis of data
Problems whose solution requires the application of statistical and other methods can be determined in the form of: 1. <i>Ongoing activities</i> (activities related to quality monitoring through defined sources of information). 2. <i>Occasional activities</i> (activities related to specially defined projects to improve the quality of products and/or processes)	Collecting data on the achieved characteristics of the quality of the tourist product and identifying problems.	It can be done in several ways, and it is most often done by periodic statistical analysis of relevant statistical measures of the achieved quality of the tourist product.

The results of the research should be used to determine the priorities that require the improvement of the quality management system.

MEASURING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES USING THE SERVQUAL MODEL

In 1988, Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry developed a service quality measurement technique known as the SERVQUAL model⁷. SERVQUAL is designed to measure service quality in a wide variety of service sector businesses: hospitality, travel and tourism, car servicing, higher education,

⁷ Swarbrooke, J., Horner, S., Consumer Behaviour in Tourism, 2007, pp. 241

hospitals, banks, government institutions, logistics, etc. Parasuraman et al developed the GAP model of service quality:

$$SQ = \sum_{i=1}^k (P_{ij} - E_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

SQ – service quality

P_{ij} – seeing the performance of stimulus i under the influence of attribute j

E_{ij} – expected service quality for attribute j in relation to set standards for stimulus i ⁸.

Picture 1. SERVQUAL model

Source: Parasuramann A., Zeithaml V.A., Berry L.L., A Conceptual Model of ServiceQuality and its Implications for Future Research, Journal of Marketing, Vo 49, No.4, New York, 1985 u Ćosić M., p. 91

According to the mentioned model, service quality is a function of the consumer's perception, i.e. the way they saw and experienced the service, and the expectations they formed before purchasing or using the service.⁹ The SERVQUAL model settled on 5 individual determinants of service quality for measuring consumer expectations and their perception: *reliability, responsibility, security, empathy, tangibility*.¹⁰ The goal of applying the SERVQUAL model is to indicate the difference between the expected and received service and to determine the differences between them. The

⁸ Veljković S. Marketing usluga, Centar za izdavačku delatnost Ekonomskog fakulteta u Beogradu, 2007

⁹ Parasuraman A, Zeithaml V. A, Berry L. L. A Conceptual of Service Quality and its Implications for Future Research, Journal of Marketing, 49 (Fall), 1985, pp. 41-50

¹⁰ Veljković S. Marketing usluga, Centar za izdavačku delatnost Ekonomskog fakulteta u Beogradu, 2007

SERVQUAL model identifies five differences (between the expected and perceived service), while the basic difference is the user's GAP that arises as a consequence of one of the four differences that arise due to deviations in a certain phase of creating and delivering the service to users.

The first difference arises as a consequence of misunderstanding the expectations of service users. The second difference arises when the managers of the organization, although they know what the service users are looking for, are unable to fulfill their wishes due to various impossibilities. The third difference appears due to the differences between the quality specification and the service provided. The fourth difference occurs due to differences between the provided service and external communication, i.e. when the organization promises more in external communications than it is able to provide. The fifth difference represents the difference between expected and received services, i.e. their quality.

To measure perceptions, a seven-point Likert scale is usually used, where at one end of the scale is the "do not agree at all" answer (1), and at the other end is the "completely agree" answer (7).

According to the SERVQUAL methodology, 22 pairs of questions are formulated, of which respondents are first asked one series of 22 questions **before** using the service, which measures **expectations**, and then, after using the service, another series of 22 questions according to the specified categories, which measures **experiences**, that is, the user's perceptions (attitudes) about the service provided.

APPLICATION OF THE MODIFIED SERVQUAL MODEL IN ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE ZLATIBOR DISTRICT

The SERVQUAL model was used as the basis for the formation of the service quality measurement model used in this research. The claims in this model can be grouped into 5 dimensions of quality, respectively:

- Tangibility – appearance of the building, equipment and employees
- Reliability – consistency of service quality
- Responsibility – willingness of employees to provide service to guests at a certain time
- Safety – knowledge, courtesy and ability of employees to instill trust and confidence
- Empathy – a caring attitude towards guests.

In order to evaluate the quality of tourist services in the Zlatibor district, an empirical research was conducted through surveys on a sample of 95 respondents. The research was conducted in the period from April 2021 to September 2021. The questionnaire was in written form and consisted of three parts. The first part of the questionnaire contained data for service users according to gender, age and education. The second part of the questionnaire included 22 statements related to user expectations and reflecting five quality dimensions taken from the original SERVQUAL model.¹¹ In the third part, 22 statements were reformulated into questions related to the perception of service quality. To measure the attitudes of users of tourist services in the Zlatibor district, a 7-point Likert scale was used, where 7 is "completely agree", while 1 is "completely disagree". For each dimension of service quality, several statements or questions were asked.

Table 2. SERVQUAL questions adapted for research

	Expectations	Realization
Tangibility	1. The tourist facility should be modernly equipped 2. The tourist facility should be visually appealing. 3. Employees in the tourist facility should be properly dressed and clean. 4. Materials related to the service of the tourist facility (brochures, price lists, food and beverage menu...) should be visually attractive.	1. The tourist facility is modernly equipped 2. The tourist facility is visually appealing. 3. Employees in the tourist facility are appropriately dressed and clean 4. Materials related to the service of the tourist facility (brochures, price lists, food and drink menu...) are visually attractive.
Reliability	5. In the tourist facility, the promises made to the guest should be fulfilled on time 6. When the guest has a problem, the facility staff should show interest in solving the problem. 7. In a tourist facility, the first service provided should be impeccable 8. In the tourist facility, services should be provided exactly at the promised time 9. In the tourist facility, services should be provided without faults	5. The tourist facility fulfils its promises on time. 6. When the guest has a problem, the facility staff shows interest in solving the problem. 7. In the tourist facility, the first service provided is impeccable. 8. In the tourist facility, services are provided exactly at the promised time 9. The services provided in the tourist facility are error-free

¹¹ Parasuraman A., Zeithaml V.A., Berry L.L., SERVQUAL: a multi-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of the service quality,, Journal of Retailing 64 (1) 12- 40,1988

Responsibility	<p>10. The staff of the tourist facility should inform the guest about the exact time the service will be provided</p> <p>11. Employees in the tourist facility should provide fast service</p> <p>12. Employees in the tourist facility should always be ready to help</p> <p>13. Employees in the tourist facility should always be in the mood for answering the guests' questions</p>	<p>10. The staff of the tourist facility informs the guest about the exact time of service</p> <p>11. Employees in the tourist facility provide fast service</p> <p>12. The employees of the tourist facility are always ready to help</p> <p>13. The employees of the tourist facility are always ready to answer questions</p>
Safety	<p>14. The behavior of the employees in the tourist facility must instill confidence in the guest</p> <p>15. Guests should feel safe while working with the staff of the tourist facility</p> <p>16. Employees in the tourist facility must always be polite to guests</p> <p>17. Employees in the tourist facility should know how to respond to every request of the guest</p>	<p>14. The behavior of the employees in the tourist facility instills trust</p> <p>15. Guests feel safe while working with the staff of the tourist facility</p> <p>16. The employees of the tourist facility are always kind to the guests</p> <p>17. The employees of the tourist facility know how to respond to every request of the guest</p>
Empathy	<p>18. Employees in the tourist facility should pay attention to each individual</p> <p>19. The working hours of the tourist facility should correspond to the needs of the guest</p> <p>20. The tourist facility should have employees who will pay special attention to the guest</p> <p>21. An employee in the tourist facility should take care of the guest</p> <p>22. Employees in the tourist facility should understand the specific needs of the guest</p>	<p>18. Employees in the tourist facility pay attention to each individual</p> <p>19. The working hours of the tourist facility correspond to the needs of the guest</p> <p>20. The tourist facility should have employees who provide the guest with special attention</p> <p>21. Employees in the tourist facility take careful care of the guest</p> <p>22. The employees of the tourist facility understand the specific needs of the guest</p>

RESEARCH RESULTS

Basic data about the interviewees

Table 3. Basic data about the interviewees

Factor	Category	%
Country	Serbia	88
	Abroad	12
Sex	Male	58
	Female	42
Age	24 and younger	13
	25-35	25
	36-45	32
	45-55	18
	56+	12

Education	Primary school	5
	Secondary school	49
	Basic academic studies	39
	Master	5
	PhD	2

As can be seen from Table 3, the largest number of respondents was from Serbia (88%), while only 12% of respondents were from abroad. Of the total number of respondents, 58% were men and 42% were women. In terms of age, the largest number of respondents was between 36-45 years old, while the highest percentage of respondents had a secondary school education (49%).

Analysis of expected and realized satisfaction with the quality of the provided tourist service

Table 4. Average ranges of expectations and perceptions of service users

	Expectations (E)									Perception (P)							(P- E)
	Range									Range							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Aver.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Aver.	
TANGIBILITY																	
1	0	0	0	12	25	24	34	5.84	0	0	0	10	25	26	34	5.88	+0.04
2	0	0	5	10	23	26	31	5.71	0	0	0	18	15	31	31	5.78	+0.07
3	0	0	2	7	26	31	29	5.82	0	0	2	8	21	35	29	5.85	+0.03
4	0	0	2	10	22	32	29	5.80	0	0	6	10	16	36	27	5.82	+0.02
Tangibility average = +0.04																	
RELIABILITY																	
5	0	0	8	12	20	26	29	5.59	0	0	11	10	18	29	27	5.53	-0.06
6	0	6	8	8	19	25	29	5.43	0	0	9	16	22	28	20	5.42	-0.01
7	4	5	9	10	18	24	25	5.16	0	0	0	16	21	30	28	5.74	+0.58
8	0	2	6	12	19	25	31	5.60	0	0	10	9	19	31	26	5.56	-0.04
9	0	1	8	11	18	24	33	5.63	0	0	8	16	21	30	20	5.40	-0.23
Reliability average = +0.05																	
RESPONSIBILITY																	
10	0	0	7	15	18	26	29	5.58	0	0	3	9	24	29	30	5.78	+0.20
11	0	8	13	19	16	19	20	4.89	0	0	2	10	23	31	29	5.79	+0.90
12	0	9	16	18	17	15	20	4.77	0	0	0	12	24	30	29	5.80	+1.03
13	0	0	12	24	15	23	21	4.76	0	0	2	11	22	29	31	5.80	+1.04
Responsibility average = +0.79																	
SAFETY																	
14	0	0	9	13	18	28	27	5.54	0	0	0	13	17	35	30	5.92	+0.38
15	0	0	10	17	16	27	25	5.42	0	0	0	11	20	34	30	5.87	+0.45
16	2	2	9	15	15	28	24	5.31	0	0	1	12	19	34	29	5.82	+0.51
17	0	0	17	14	20	22	22	5.19	0	0	3	11	20	31	30	5.78	+0.59
Safety average = 0.48																	
EMPATHY																	
18	9	9	10	25	10	19	13	4.34	0	0	10	13	16	27	29	5.58	+1.24
19	3	8	21	14	9	20	20	4.66	0	10	7	22	21	20	15	4.83	+0.17
20	6	7	14	14	19	16	19	4.65	0	0	14	18	22	21	20	5.16	+0.51
21	7	8	18	17	10	15	20	4.47	0	0	11	17	26	21	20	5.23	+0.76
22	6	8	14	21	11	14	21	4.57	0	1	12	16	22	23	21	5.23	+0.66
Empathy average = 0.67																	
TOTAL AVERAGE = +0.41																	

DISCUSSION

The results obtained were compared for each of the questions and for each of the five dimensions. In the end, the final result was obtained and it shows us the difference of perception and expectations of the clients. The positive result obtained at the end shows that the clients got more than they expected.

Questions 1-4 were about tangibility and the final average is +0.04.

Questions 5-9 were about reliability. The final average is +0.05. This aspect is important because reliability is the most important dimension for services provided to consumers (Bateson and Hoffman, 2001, Lovelock, 2001).

Questions 10-13 were about responsibility and had an average of + 0.79. The difference to all the questions asked was positive, which shows that the services are at a good level and that the tourist facilities have high-quality staff.

Questions 14-17 in the adapted SERVQUAL model were related to safety and had an overall average of +0.48.

Questions 18-22 were related to empathy, and the average obtained was +0.67. The positive results show that attention is paid to the users of the services and that the tourist facilities try to fulfill the needs of the users of their services.

The overall average for all five dimensions is +0.41. In Table 5, we can see the difference between expected and perceived service quality.

Table 5. The difference between expected and perceived service quality (SERVQUAL gap)

Quality determinants	Perception (P)	Rank	Expectation (E)	Rank	SERVQUAL gap = P-E
Tangibility	5.83	2	5.79	1	+0.04
Reliability	5.53	4	5.48	2	+0.05
Responsibility	5.79	3	5.00	4	+0.79
Safety	5.85	1	5.37	3	+0.48
Empathy	5.20	5	4.54	5	+0.67
Total SERVQUAL gap	5.64		5.23		+0.41

CONCLUSION

Attracting and retaining users of tourist services in today's business conditions is possible only if tourist facilities provide high-quality services with a special focus on meeting the needs of users. By measuring user satisfaction with the service provided, tourist facilities or individuals can obtain accurate data on the quality of the service provided, and based on this, they can take effective measures to improve the quality of their services, which should result in a better offer and increase in demand.

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